

Comprehensive Architecture for Data Quality Assessment in Industrial IoT

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Abstract—The rapid growth of the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) has led to the generation of vast amounts of data, which has significant implications for decision-making in various industrial sectors and is increasingly being traded on data marketplaces. Quantifying IIoT data quality and providing measures to improve, it is critical for both operational efficiency and business value. This paper presents a comprehensive architecture for data quality assessment in the IIoT, aimed at ensuring the quality, trustworthiness, and reliability of the data generated by the IIoT. The architecture facilitates both objective and subjective assessments, taking into account the intended task for the data, and includes data enhancement operations to address data quality issues. The architecture provides a standardized and modular approach to data quality evaluation, allowing data owners and data market participants to make informed decisions about the quality and value of their data. The proposed architecture has the potential to significantly impact various industrial sectors and data marketplaces, providing a valuable tool for ensuring the reliability and accuracy of IIoT data. As the architecture is a work in progress, the preliminary evaluation of its effectiveness has been omitted for future work.

Index Terms—Industrial Internet of Things, Data Quality, Data curation

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid expansion of the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) has ushered in a new era of data-driven decision-making across a wide range of industries, including manufacturing, smart cities, precision farming, and healthcare [1]. The integration of IoT devices, sensors, and advanced analytics has enabled organizations to optimize their operations, enhance efficiency, and drive innovation [2]. However, the growing volume and complexity of data generated by IIoT systems have introduced new challenges in ensuring the reliability and quality of this data [3] [4] [5]. Moreover, data quality (DQ) is often undervalued and not incentivized, despite being a critical aspect that affects Artificial Intelligence (AI) development. This results in organizations failing to meet DQ standards, and AI developers spending excessive time on data tasks [6].

High-quality data is paramount to the success of any IIoT system, as it determines the performance, fairness, robustness, and safety of AI systems [7]. For example, the development of accurate predictive models often depends on the identification and analysis of abnormal data points [8]. However, IoT-based datasets primarily consist of normal data or data that

is uncorrelated to valuable insights as well as missing or extreme data points, leading to imbalanced datasets, biased model training, and underperforming predictive models. Thus, there is a need for DQ assessment tools that can effectively determine the suitability of data for a specific task, ensuring more reliable and robust models [9].

Furthermore, the growing trend of data marketplaces, where organizations buy, sell, and trade data assets, emphasizes the crucial importance of trust between data sellers and buyers. This trust can only be established through reliable DQ assessment and pricing mechanisms [10]. To facilitate this, advanced tools and techniques are required to evaluate and price data assets based on their quality, taking into account various factors such as volume, completeness, locality, context, variety, and industrial application usage. This not only ensures that data buyers purchase data assets that are suitable for their specific use cases, but also provides sellers with transparent pricing models that enable them to effectively monetize their data assets.

The current focus in DQ assessment has mainly been on objective data dimensions, such as volume, completeness, locality, context, and variety. However, most available DQ tools, such as Talend [11], Informatica, and IBM InfoSphere [12], do not consider the specific tasks that the data are intended to fulfill. While there are specialized tools designed for particular tasks, such as Prophet for time-series forecasting [13], they often lack the necessary flexibility (i.e., the input data should have specific format) for broader applications. As a result, there is a need for a more comprehensive and versatile approach to DQ assessment that can accommodate various tasks and contexts while maintaining high levels of trust and reliability in data.

The proposed architecture for DQ assessment in IIoT offers several key benefits for users and stakeholders involved in data-driven decision-making processes. It combines objective and subjective assessment methods, enabling a more holistic evaluation of DQ. This, in turn, leads to enhanced trust in industrial data and improved decision-making capabilities. Additionally, the architecture provides tools for enhancing the DQ, allowing organizations to address issues such as missing and erroneous data values and optimize the quality of their data assets. The combination of DQ assessment and improvement

capabilities makes the architecture a valuable tool for organizations looking to maximize the value of their data. What is more, specific architecture components, presented in the following sections, can be used in the form of data pipelines to automate DQ assessment processes required by the data marketplaces.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II provides an overview of the related work and specialized tools for DQ assessment, highlighting the limitations of existing approaches. Section III presents the proposed architecture for DQ assessment in IIoT, including a detailed description of its components, functions, and features. Section IV explores the applications and use cases of the proposed architecture, including its potential impact and benefits for data owners and data marketplaces. Finally, Section V concludes the paper and outlines the future work that is needed to further develop and validate the proposed architecture.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Approaches to Data Quality Assessment in IIoT Context

To ensure high DQ in the IIoT context, dedicated data assessment and profiling is essential to uncover inconsistencies, inaccuracies, incompleteness, and other anomalies in the data. Approaches to DQ assessment should consider both objective and subjective data aspects, as outlined in [14]. However, most existing works focus only on objective DQ dimensions, such as data accuracy, completeness, consistency, timeliness, validity, and uniqueness [15]. DataPref [16], recognizing the need for high-quality data in AI, is developing a benchmark suite for Machine Learning (ML) datasets, as is Kaggle for ML models. It benchmarks the datasets based on the accuracy of the ML models that applied to them as well as subsets of them.

In the IIoT domain, data characteristics are highly dependent on their context and are typically characterized by smooth variation, continuity, correlation, seasonality, and Markovian behavior [17]. These data modalities cannot be effectively quantified by standard DQ metrics. A review presented in [18] highlights the need for context and domain-aware DQ to enable trusted peer-to-peer (P2P) data sharing in the IoT. The notion of trusted IoT data sharing is also highly relevant to data marketplaces. The DQIoT framework [19] focuses on managing DQ when IoT data is consumed directly from other services. This framework, consisting of an acquisition, processing, and utilization layer, aims to address several DQ issues that arise in IoT environments, such as inconsistencies in data sensing.

B. Data Profiling Tools

Data profiling is the process of examining, analyzing, and summarizing datasets to understand their structure, content, quality, and relationships between attributes. There have been several tools developed to facilitate data profiling, with some focusing on specific data types, such as structured or unstructured data, while others cater to a broader range of data sources.

OpenRefine [20] is a Java-based open-source tool for data cleaning and transformation, often employed for data profiling tasks. It enables users to explore large datasets, identify patterns, and clean or transform data using a web-based interface. OpenRefine supports various data formats and connections to databases (using SQL). Apache DataSketches can be leveraged for big data analysis through approximation via sketch algorithms specifically designed for production environments [21]. Various commercial tools offer similar functionalities and may provide additional features. For example, Paxata's Self-Service Data Preparation allows visual interactions for data filtering tasks, enhancing user experience and Trifacta's Wrangler predicts data patterns to aid users in data transformation [22]. Due to the importance of data profiling, many data management solutions and Extract-Transform-Load (ETL) tools have built-in profiling capabilities [23], such as SAP's HANA, IBM's Information Analyzer, and Microsoft's SQL Server Integration Services (SSIS).

C. Data Profiling Libraries

Python, as the most prominent programming language for data analytics, boasts several libraries that facilitate data profiling tasks required by tools that are based on the proposed architecture. Notably, whylogs is particularly suited for large-scale datasets and machine learning applications [24]. It is designed to work with both batch and streaming data, making it suitable for various data types and real-time data analysis. Whylogs captures statistical summaries and distributions of data features, allowing users to track DQ, identify issues, and monitor changes over time. Ydata-profiling [25] is another open-source library that generates reports with descriptive statistics and visualizations for each column in a dataframe, enabling timely understanding of the data's structure and content. In addition to schema identification and data analysis, DataProfiler detects sensitive data using a pre-trained deep learning model for name entity recognition (NER) [26]. It outputs the profile of the given data in JSON format, allowing integration with more complex pipelines. The Great Expectations framework validates input data against predefined rules or requirements, helping to catch errors early in a data pipeline and ensuring data conforms to expectations.

D. Time Series Data Profiling Tools and Libraries

Time series data is a prevalent type of data generated by IoT devices, sensors, and systems. This type of data often requires specialized tools and techniques for profiling, analysis, and visualization, making time series profiling an essential component of DQ assessment in the context of IIoT. One such tool is Microsoft Azure TSI, which is a fully managed analytics, storage, and visualization service that enables users to explore and analyze large-scale time series data in real-time, offering rich visualization and querying capabilities [27]. Another prominent library, TSFRESH, is an open-source Python solution that automates the feature extraction and selection process from time series data. By doing so, it assists users in identifying important characteristics and patterns without

the need for extensive domain knowledge [28]. Darts [29] is a time series forecasting library that provides an easy-to-use interface for time series data analysis and forecasting. It incorporates built-in support for handling seasonal patterns, holidays, and other time-based events that may impact the data. DeepVaR framework could be used to assess the volatility of multiple time series, such as data from IoT sensors in parallel [30]. These tools and libraries, specifically designed for time series data, are well-suited for profiling and analyzing data in applications such as finance, energy, retail, and (I)IoT, among others.

This section’s review of existing DQ assessment methods and data profiling tools reveals the complexity of ensuring high DQ, particularly within the IIoT context. While these methods and tools offer key functionalities, they typically focus on individual aspects of DQ management, and may not be fit for data marketplace scenarios requiring standardized and transparent assessments. In response, this work proposes an adaptable architecture for DQ assessment that considers both objective and task-specific dimensions, incorporates data profiling functionalities and enables informed decisions about enhancing DQ.

III. ARCHITECTURE DESIGN

The proposed architecture for a comprehensive DQ assessment tool encompasses a modular design that facilitates seamless integration of various components to address the challenges associated with DQ in IIoT. These components, illustrated in Fig. 1, include Data Load, Data Operations, Objective Assessment, Quality Assessment, Quality Score, Data Profiling, and User Interface.

The Data Load component is responsible for collecting and ingesting data from various sources while the Data Operations component carries out necessary functions to complement the assessment process and improve DQ. The Objective and Quality Assessment components perform evaluations of the data based on objective dimensions and task-specific criteria, respectively. The Quality Score component generates a comprehensive scoring per quality dimension and category that reflects the overall quality of the data in the context of the specified task. The Data Profiling component generates a comprehensive summary of the dataset’s characteristics and properties assisting users to better understand their data and identify any patterns or anomalies that might impact their quality or utility. Finally, the User Interface provides a platform for users to interact with the system and input their requirements.

The following subsections delve into the details of each of these components, discussing their functionalities, design considerations, and their role in contributing to a versatile and comprehensive approach to DQ assessment.

A. Data Load

The Data Load component (DL) handles the initial ingestion of data from various sources and is responsible for proper collection, loading, and formatting of data for further processing and assessment within the system. The component integrates

with a variety of data sources, including relational databases, NoSQL databases, APIs, and file systems, and accommodates different data formats such as CSV, JSON, and Parquet. The component converts these formats into a unified representation for seamless processing within the system.

Additionally, the DL extracts the data schema, which encompasses information about the data structure, data types, and relationships between fields. Depending on the use case, the component could utilize partitioning, parallelism, and sampling techniques to manage large datasets and guarantee efficient processing effectively. The data are divided into smaller chunks, allowing multiple instances of the assessment and operations components to process them concurrently, thereby enhancing performance and scalability.

Sampling methods, including random sampling and stratified sampling, can be employed to select a representative subset of the data for processing, reducing computational overhead and streamlining the assessment process. The choice of sampling method depends on the nature of the dataset and the specific requirements of the DQ assessment task.

B. Data Operations

The Data Operations component (DO) implements processing tasks necessary for the DQ assessment and enhancement of the input dataset, as well as efficient data profiling. It performs a set of predefined checks and transformations to assist the Objective and Quality Assessment components in evaluating the dataset more efficiently and accurately.

These checks and transformations may include data type verification to ensure that data values are of the correct type, data filtering and formatting to remove or modify irrelevant or inconsistent data. These tasks help ensure that the DQ assessment and data profiling processes are accurate and comprehensive. In addition to these checks and transformations, it also provides a set of available DQ improvement operations, such as data cleansing, aggregation and augmentation, feature engineering, missing values imputation, data transformation, and outlier detection and handling. Users can select the desired operations and reassess the quality of their dataset, improving its overall quality and utility.

C. Objective Assessment

The Objective Assessment module (OA) plays a crucial role in evaluating DQ based on several objective dimensions. It scrutinizes the input data across five key aspects: completeness, accuracy, consistency, timeliness, and variety.

Completeness refers to the measure of the dataset’s extent in encompassing all required data points and attributes. The absence of necessary data points can severely affect the performance of predictive maintenance and anomaly detection tasks. Accuracy pertains to the correctness of data values and their freedom from errors which are common in IoT data due to various factors such as sensor failures or uncalibrated sensors. High data accuracy is crucial for precise and reliable results of AI systems leveraging these data.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Architecture for Comprehensive Data Quality Assessment.

Consistency focuses on the uniformity in data format, units, and representation across different data sources and records. This uniformity allows for accurate comparisons, aggregation, and analysis within the system. Timeliness evaluates the degree to which the data are current and relevant for the tasks at hand. In the dynamic environment of IIoT, timely data are essential for identifying emerging issues and making proactive decisions.

Variety examines the diversity of data types (numerical, categorical, unstructured) and sources included in the dataset. A rich mix of data sources and types can provide a more comprehensive view of the system's performance and health, enhancing the effectiveness of IIoT tasks such as predictive maintenance and anomaly detection.

D. Subjective Assessment

The Subjective Assessment component (SA) plays a critical role in evaluating the quality of the input dataset and determining its suitability for specific tasks, such as time series prediction, classification or anomaly detection. This component assesses the input dataset based on task-specific metrics that are relevant to the intended use case.

For time series prediction, the SA may evaluate the dataset's temporal patterns and autocorrelation structure to ensure that it is suitable for training and validating predictive models. Feature importance analysis may also be used to identify which features in the dataset are most relevant for the prediction task. Dataset's class distribution and balance can provide insights whether it is suitable for training and validating classification models. The assessment may also evaluate the feature importance and mutual information between features to ensure that the dataset contains sufficient discriminative information to distinguish between different classes. For anomaly detection tasks, the assessment could include evaluation of the dataset's signal-to-noise ratio and distributional properties to ensure that it is suitable for detecting anomalous behavior. Likewise, temporal dynamics and relationships between different features

may provide insights whether the dataset contains sufficient information to detect anomalies.

In addition, the SA may quantify the DQ based on the performance score of machine learning algorithms applied to the data under evaluation. For example, if the given dataset is intended for anomaly detection in machinery, the Isolation Forest algorithm could be applied to the dataset during the SA [31], and the resulting anomaly score contribute to the DQ scoring.

Hence, SA evaluates the input dataset's suitability for the task and identifies any deficiencies or inconsistencies that may affect its suitability, allowing data owners to take appropriate actions to improve the DQ. SA is also crucial for buyers of datasets as it evaluates the quality and suitability of the dataset based on task-specific metrics, allowing buyers to make informed decisions on the usefulness of the dataset for their intended use case.

E. Quality Score

The Quality Score module provides a detailed evaluation of the input dataset's quality by generating scores for each DQ dimension and category based on the inputs from the Objective and Subjective Assessment. Specifically, the Quality Score generates scores for each of the five objective dimensions and for each subjective category, scaled similarly across all dimensions and categories.

To generate the overall quality score for the dataset, the scores for each dimension and category are combined and weighted based on their importance for the specific task. The weighting of the scores can be determined using methods such as expert judgment, decision trees, or machine learning algorithms. For example, expert judgment can be used to determine the importance of each dimension and category based on the specific requirements of the task at hand. Alternatively, decision trees or machine learning algorithms can be used to learn the importance of each dimension and category from historical data or through training on a labeled dataset.

By providing scores for each dimension and category at similar scales, the Quality Score component enables users to compare and rank different datasets based on their quality across a wide range of metrics. This standardized approach provides a clear and quantitative measure for evaluating the quality and worth of datasets, enabling users to make more informed decisions about their data-related activities.

F. Data Profiling

The Data Profiling component (DP) generates a comprehensive summary of the dataset's characteristics and properties, which is then fed to the User Interface. This information enables users to better understand the structure, content, and quality of their data, allowing them to make informed decisions regarding DQ improvement operations.

The component calculates various descriptive statistics for each column in the dataset, such as mean, median, mode, standard deviation, and percentiles. These statistics provide a snapshot of the data's central tendency, variability, and distribution. The DP also generates a detailed report, which consolidates the descriptive statistics and DQ metrics into a single, easy-to-understand document. This report is designed to be consumed by the User Interface and provides users with a comprehensive view of the dataset's characteristics and quality. The report includes information such as the number of records and columns in the dataset, the data types for each column, and the results of the descriptive statistics.

The DP plays a crucial role in the proposed architecture, providing users with a comprehensive and actionable view of the dataset's characteristics and quality. The generated information is ready to be visualized by the User Interface, providing users with an interactive view of the data.

G. User Interface

The User Interface (UI) is the primary interface between the user and the system, providing a platform for users to interact with the system and input their requirements. Users can specify the intended task for their data, such as forecasting, anomaly detection, or classification, as well as any associated parameters, such as dataset metadata and linked datasets. This enables the system to tailor the DQ assessment process to meet the specific requirements of each task. The UI includes a range of reporting and visualization tools to help users interpret the DQ assessment results. This includes summary reports, quality score breakdowns, and visualizations of the data, such as bar charts, histograms, scatter and box plots, enabling users to gain insights into the DQ and make informed decisions about its suitability for their specific tasks. The visualizations provided by the UI are dynamic and interactive, allowing users to explore and understand the data in a meaningful manner.

IV. APPLICATION AND USE CASES

The proposed architecture for DQ assessment has the potential to make a significant impact and be applied in various settings, making it suitable for both data owners and participants in data marketplaces.

Data owners can develop tools based on this architecture to assess, enhance or monitor the quality of their datasets. The modular design and the ability to perform both objective and subjective assessments provide a comprehensive evaluation of the data's quality, allowing data owners to identify the strengths and weaknesses of their datasets. This information can be used to make informed decisions about improving the DQ and boosting the performance of predictive models relying on these data.

Data marketplaces can also benefit from the architecture by using it to establish pipelines for comparing and evaluating datasets. As depicted in Fig. 2, data marketplaces can leverage specific components and functions of the architecture, such as the Data Load, Data Operations, Objective Assessment, Subjective Assessment, and Quality Score modules, to create pipelines that automate and streamline the quality assessment of hosted datasets. The standardized approach to evaluating DQ and the ability to provide scores for each dimension and category enable data marketplaces to rank and compare datasets in a transparent and quantitative manner. This information can be used to inform buying and selling decisions and provide a better understanding of the quality and value of the datasets traded.

Fig. 2. Indicative Quality Assessment pipeline.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This work introduces an architecture for DQ assessment that is designed to address the challenges commonly found in IIoT datasets. The modular design and ability to perform both objective and subjective assessments provide a comprehensive evaluation of the data's quality, which is especially important in the dynamic and complex environment of IIoT. This evaluation allows data owners to identify the strengths and weaknesses of their datasets and make informed decisions about how to improve their DQ, leading to more reliable and accurate predictive models.

Furthermore, the standardized approach to evaluating DQ and ability to provide scores for each dimension and category help to address the issue of data diversity and complexity in IIoT, enabling data marketplaces to rank and price datasets based on multiple quality dimensions. This information can be used to inform buying and selling decisions in a trusted manner while ensuring that traded data are of high quality and suitable for the intended use.

Future work on this architecture will focus on its implementation and realization in real-world use cases. This will

involve testing and validating the architecture on diverse and complex datasets from the IIoT domain (i.e., smart grids [32], manufacturing [33], oil & gas [34]), with the aim of demonstrating its effectiveness and efficiency in assessing and improving the quality of these datasets. Furthermore, efforts will be made to extend the architecture to accommodate new DQ dimensions and categories that may emerge as the IIoT domain evolves such as privacy, security, and ethical considerations in the data handling process. Through these ongoing efforts, the architecture aims to stay in tune with the latest developments in the field, thereby striving to effectively address the diverse needs of different industrial sectors and data marketplaces. Another avenue of future work will be to integrate the architecture with existing IIoT platforms and marketplaces such as FAME [35], enabling seamless integration and deployment of the DQ assessment process within these systems. This integration is expected to further streamline the process of evaluating and improving the quality of IIoT datasets, making it more accessible for data owners and market participants.

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